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Genomics in Switzerland

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Overview of Research in Genomics in Switzerland and Prospects for Scientific Cooperation with Canada

Prepared for
Genome Canada

Science-Metrix

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514.495.6505 ▪ 4572 avenue de Lorimier ▪ Montréal ▪ Québec ▪ Canada ▪ H2H 2B5
info@science-metrix.com ▪ www.science-metrix.com

Executive Summary

This report on genome research in Switzerland uses public information sources available on the Internet, such as the Medline database, and data from the Science Citation Index and the United States Patent and Trademark Office.

The first section presents an overview of genomic research programmes. Unlike Canadian genomic research, Swiss genome research is not funded by a specific government program or by a non-governmental organization. In Switzerland, genome research is financed by government programmes that provide funds for research at large. In spite of this, Swiss genomics grew steadily during the last decade. Part I also presents data from the Internet on Swiss institutions that are active in the field.

Section II compares Switzerland's position in genomics to that of Canada and other leading countries. A series of scientometric and technometric indicators shows that given their converging strengths Canada and Switzerland can enter mutually beneficial collaborative activities in a number of scientific specialties, particularly within the field of biomedical research (e.g. biomedical engineering) as well as in clinical medicine (e.g. nephrology, neurology and neurosurgery).

Drawing from the Medline database, Section 3 examines the distribution of papers in genomics by sector, institution, city, and researcher. The distribution of research in genomics in Switzerland is concentrated in two locations:

- Zürich: its output of papers is unmatched; it hosts the two leading universities, one of the seven leading health-sector organizations, and more than two-thirds of the leading researchers.
- Basel: it has the second largest paper output by city and is responsible for more than 80% of output by the private sector.

Other Swiss urban centres with significant output comprise Genève, Lausanne, and Bern.

One of the salient aspects of the field of genomics in Switzerland is the presence of two Nobel laureates amongst the leaders and three researchers who appear on ISI's Highly Cited list. Another salient feature is the high proportion of scientific output by the private sector: with 14% of scientific papers, the proportion published by firms is about seven times larger than in countries such as Sweden and the Netherlands and is similar to that of Denmark, which also stands out in this respect.

The views presented in this report are those of Science-Metrix and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of Genome Canada.

I. An Overview of Genomics in Switzerland

Switzerland's has long been honoured for its neutrality by the major European powers. It was not, for instance, involved in either of the two World Wars. But the political and economic integration of Europe over the past fifty year and Switzerland's role in many UN and international organizations may be rendering obsolete the country's concern for neutrality. Switzerland's economy is stable and prosperous, with a gross domestic product (GDP) per capita that is 20% higher than that of the big Western European nations. Recently, Switzerland brought its economic practices into conformity with these of the European Union (EU) to enhance its international competitiveness. Although the Swiss are not pursuing full EU membership in the near term, in 1999, Bern and Brussels signed agreements to further liberalize trade. These agreements came into force in 2001 (CIA. 2001. *The World Factbook 2001*).

Switzerland's population is about a quarter that of Canada (Table 1). About half the total population in both countries forms their respective labour force. The Swiss GDP per capita – among the highest worldwide – is higher than Canada's by almost US \$4,000.

Table 1 Basic Socio-Economic Statistics

	Switzerland	Canada
Area (sq km)	41,290	9,976,140
Population (July 2001 est.)	7,283,274	31,592,805
Labour force (2000)	3,900,000 (53% of pop.)	16,100,000 (51%)
GDP*	US \$207 billion	US \$775 billion
GDP per capita*	US \$28,600	US \$24,800
Government type	Federal republic	Parliamentary democracy

* Purchasing power parity – 2000 est.
Source: CIA. 2001. *The World Factbook 2001*.

Between 1990 and 2001, Switzerland published 16,990 papers in genomics that were indexed by Medline (measured by first author of paper and Swiss affiliation). This compares to 38,248 papers by Canadian authors during the same period. Figure 1 reveals that the output of papers in genomics in Switzerland grew slightly more rapidly than in Canada during the 1990s: 7.6% average annual growth in Switzerland compared to 6.7 % in Canada.

National Research Programmes in Genomics

At the end of 1998, the Swiss Federal Council, with the goal to maintain Switzerland's strengths in research, mandated the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)¹ to launch a new programme promoting scientific excellence and the development of closer ties between academic institutions and the public and private sectors. This led to the creation in 1999 of a programme called National Centres of Competence in Research (NCCR). Although present in some of the NCCR, genomics is not a core aspect of the SNSF's Pluriannual Programme 2004-2007.

Importantly though, "Frontiers in Genetics" is one of the 14 NCCR currently active in Switzerland. Its statutes consist of a tripartite contractual agreement signed in 2001 between SNSF, University of Geneva (home institution) and NCCR Genetics². "Frontiers in Genetics" comprises four platforms: Genomics; Proteomics; Bio-imaging; Mammalian Genetics. The NCCR hosts 13 research groups in the Lake Lemman region, and 2 laboratories in Zürich.

¹ The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNF) was created in 1952 by the Federal Council of the Swiss Government. The SNF, which operates according to the principle of scientific independence, is a central player in publicly funded research. The primary focus of its activities is promoting independent basic research and young scientific talents. With its interdisciplinary and problem-oriented research programmes, the SNF attempts to provide scientifically sound solutions to problems of social significance and to develop scientific centres of excellence for specific subject areas. The Pluriannual Programmes define the principal themes for research promotion policy over the medium and long term.

² The participants are the University of Geneva (UNIGE, home institution), the University of Lausanne (UNIL), the University of Zürich, the Swiss Institute for Experimental Cancer Research (ISREC), the Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne (EPFL), the University of Geneva's Transfer of Technology office (Unitec) and the SIB (Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics).

Structure and organization of NCCR “Frontiers in Genetics”

For the first 4 years starting July 2001, the funding of this NCCR is as follow:

- SNSF (Swiss National Science Foundation, federal funds): 18.5 million Francs
- Self-funding by home institution (University of Geneva): 2.4 million Francs
- Self funding by project participants: 25.9 million Francs

Two other NCCR projects involved in fields related to genomics are the NCCR - Molecular Oncology ("Molecular Oncology – From Basic Research to Therapeutic Approaches")³, and the NCCR Structural Biology ("Molecular life science - Three Dimensional Structure, Folding and Interactions")⁴.

Genome Research in Universities

Without a doubt, Zürich is the leader in university research in genomics. Key contributors are the *Universität Zürich* (Unizh) and the *Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich* (ETHZ - Swiss Federal Institute of Technology). The Functional Genomics Center Zürich (FGCZ) is jointly sponsored by ETHZ and Unizh and provides joint access to transcriptomics, proteomics, and bioinformatics technologies.

At Unizh, the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine hosts the Proteomics Center performing research in the fields of biochemistry, genetics, molecular and cell biology, physiology, pharmacology, virology, bacteriology, pathophysiology and all clinical disciplines of veterinary medicine. Research activities of the Plant Molecular Biology department include the study of the genetic regulation of genomic imprinting and sequence analysis of large fragments of the wheat genome using DNA microarrays. The Institute of Molecular Biology performs research in developmental genetics, transcription and gene regulation, pathogenesis and gene therapy.

In the ETHZ, the Department of Biology hosts several institutes⁵ active in genomics, proteomics and/or biotechnology, and the Institute of Animal Sciences (Department of Agriculture and Food Science) works on cytogenetics, gene mapping, applications of biotechnics, molecular genetic diagnostics and statistical animal genetics. Within the Department of Mathematics, the Reverse Engineering of Genetic Regulatory Networks Project aims to further the understanding of complex genetic regulatory networks, through the integration of expanding biological data sets. The local team of interdisciplinary biological and computational experts is led by Prof. P. Bühlmann.

In Basel, the Biozentrum (University of Basel, Unibas) is a major modern biology research centre that performs genomics, proteomics, bioinformatics - related research in a wide range of fields such

³ Participant institutions of this NCCR are: the Swiss Institute for Experimental Cancer Research (ISREC, home institution), the Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research (LICR), the Institute of Biochemistry of the University of Lausanne (IB). These NCCR member institutions, together with the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB), founded the Biomedical Research Centre in Epalinges (close to Lausanne) which is one of the largest biological research campuses in Switzerland. Started in May 2001, this NCCR has a four-year budget of 36,708,236 Francs.

⁴ The University of Zürich is the home institution of this NCCR while participant institutions are the ETH Zürich, the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI Villigen) and the University of Basel. Started in May 2001, this NCCR has a four-year budget of 29,968,480 Francs.

⁵ The Institute for Molecular Biology & Biophysics, the Institute of Biotechnology, the Institute of Cell Biology, the Institute of Biochemistry and the Institute of Microbiology Institute of Toxicology.

as cell biology, bioinformatics, structural biology, molecular microbiology, applied microbiology, biochemistry and biophysical chemistry. As part of the NCCR Frontiers in Genetics, the University of Geneva's *Département de zoologie et de biologie animale*⁶ and *Département de biologie moléculaire*⁷ and University of Lausanne's *Institut de biologie animale*⁸ are highly active loci of genomics and proteomics research. Also part of this NCCR, the University of Lausanne hosts the *Centre intégratif de génomique bactérienne* comprising the *Institut de microbiologie fondamentale*⁹ and different institutes, groups and laboratories active in the field of genomics and proteomics. The internet site of university departments active in genome research are presented in Annex I.

Genome Research in the Health and Hospital Sector

In addition to hosting the Swiss Proteomic Society¹⁰, the *Hôpitaux Universitaires de Genève*¹¹ (HUG) have set genetics and genomics as priorities in their development programme for 2002-2006. Functional genomics applied to the study of *S. aureus* and the analysis of gene expression during acute bacterial infections are among the research interests of the Genomic Research Laboratory of the Division of Infectious Disease¹². The Department of Genetics and Microbiology¹³ is active in genomics and proteomics, the Department of Medical Biochemistry¹⁴ concentrates on proteomics, while the Division of Medical Genetics¹⁵ focuses on the role of genes in human disorders.

The *Universitätsspital Zürich*¹⁶ hosts a significant number of institutes active in genomics and/or proteomics. The Institute of Neuropathology¹⁷ is leading studies on the intricacies of prion neuroinvasion using the latest tools of functional genomics (high-throughput transcriptional analysis using DNA microarrays, proteomics and representational difference analysis). The

⁶ <http://www.unige.ch/sciences/biologie/biani/>

⁷ <http://www.molbio.unige.ch/>

⁸ http://www.unil.ch/iba/en_index.htm

⁹ A combination of the former Institute of Genetics and Microbial Biology (IGBM, <http://www.unil.ch/igbm/english.html>) and Laboratoire de biologie microbienne (LBM <http://www.unil.ch/lbm/>)

¹⁰ See section on Genomic Research in Governmental and Non-Governmental Organizations.

¹¹ <http://www.hug-ge.ch/www/fr/webhug.nsf>. Note that the HUG are also partner in the NCCR-Molecular Oncology.

¹² http://infobi.hcuge.ch/QuickPlace/medinter/PageLibraryC1256B3D003E3678.nsf/h_Toc/cc76097a0192cb0bc1256b6b00407da5/?OpenDocument

¹³ <http://www.genmi.unige.ch/>

¹⁴ <http://www.expasy.org/BIOMED/>

¹⁵ <http://medgen.unige.ch/>

¹⁶ *Universitätsspital Zürich* is a very close partner in the research activities of the University of Zürich's Medical Faculty. Concretely, practically all research activities of the Universitätsspital are lead within this faculty's different departments.

¹⁷ <http://www.unizh.ch/pathol/neuropathologie/index.html>

Institute of Clinical Pathology¹⁸ hosts a research project on genomic alterations associated with the prognosis of prostatic neoplasms using comparative genomic hybridization (CGH) and fluorescence in-situ hybridization (FISH). At the Physiologisches Institut¹⁹, proteomic tools are used in the determinations of multimeric protein complexes involved in apical sorting and endocytosis.

As for the *Centre hospitalier universitaire vaudois* (CHUV, Lausanne), the *Unité de Génétique Moléculaire*²⁰ performs research in both genomics and proteomics. Research in those fields and in bioinformatics will benefit from the opening of the *Centre Intégréatif de Génomique (Projet triangulaire*, see National Research Programmes in Genomics) to be located in Dorigny near Lausanne.

Finally, Switzerland is home to the Office of Information Technology of the non-for-profit international organization Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research²¹. The Office, closely associated with the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics in Lausanne and Geneva, provides scientific and administrative support to the Institute's branches and programs in the field of information technology, with a strong emphasis on bioinformatics and genomics

Genome Research in Governmental and Non-Governmental Organizations

The Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics²² (SIB) is a non-for-profit academic foundation whose mission it is to promote research, develop databanks, computer technologies and teaching and service activities in the field of bioinformatics. The Institute is closely associated with the universities of Geneva and Lausanne, the Swiss Institute for Cancer Research (ISREC), the Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research and different companies based in Switzerland. The Institute hosts a proteomics server, the ExPASy (Expert Protein Analysis System)²³, dedicated to the analysis of protein sequences and structures and 2-D PAGE.

The Swiss Proteomic Society²⁴, located at the University Medical Centre (HUG) in Genève promotes research and education in proteomics in Switzerland by facilitating the exchange of scientific information between biochemists, molecular biologists, biologists, chemists and related scientists. The Swiss Institute for Experimental Cancer Research²⁵ (ISREC), located in Lausanne, is a non-

¹⁸ <http://www.research-projects.unizh.ch/med/unit43100/area108/p203.htm>

¹⁹ <http://www.research-projects.unizh.ch/med/unit43400/index.htm>

²⁰ <http://www.hospvd.ch/public/chuv/genmol/home.htm>

²¹ <http://www.licr.org/index.htm>

²² <http://www.isb-sib.ch/structure.html>

²³ <http://ca.expasy.org/>

²⁴ <http://www.swissproteomicsociety.org/>

²⁵ <http://isrec.ch/>

profit organization subsidized by the Swiss Confederation. ISREC is the nucleus of a research complex in Epalinges near Lausanne, representing one of the most important centres of biological research in Switzerland. It includes the Institute of Biochemistry of the University of Lausanne, the WHO (World Health Organisation) Centre for Training and Research in Immunology, the Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research and the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics. Finally, the Paul Scherrer Institut²⁶, a multi-disciplinary research centre for natural sciences and technology, hosts the Structural Biology Group, active in the field of proteomics.

Genome Research in the Private Sector

In Switzerland, as in most other leading countries, government efforts in genomics research include the promotion of interaction between research institutions and industrial partners. All NCCR programmes have the explicit objective of favouring spin-offs through the different universities' transfer of technology offices²⁷, which provide help in the various matters surrounding spin-off company creation.

The significant number of firms in genomics, proteomics and biotechnology on Swiss territory led to the creation of regional organizations that are strongly committed to technology transfer, to fostering cooperation between public and private organizations and to clustering of competencies. Among those regional organizations are: Bioalps (Geneva region); BioValley (Basel and North western region); *Biopôle* (Lausanne region); and ProteomeValley (Geneva area and the Swiss plateau)²⁸. In their respective geographical areas, these organizations are all explicitly aiming to establish a dynamic corporate activity.

* * *

Switzerland has some well-established research hubs in genomics, especially in Zurich. Although research activities in genomics are not supervised via a nation-wide, systematic and explicit programme, Switzerland has invested in the field of genomics through the activities of a small number of National Centres of Competence in Research (NCCR) which might support the development of a strong research hub in the Geneva region.

²⁶ http://www.psi.ch/index_e.shtml

²⁷ Swiss transfer of technology offices of major universities comprise : Unitec (University of Geneva, <http://www.unige.ch/unitec/english/>), Unitecra (Universities of Zürich and Bern, http://www.unitecra.ch/en/index_en.htm), Pactt - technology transfer (Université de Lausanne and CHUV, <http://www.pactt.ch/>).

²⁸ Bioalps: <http://www.bioalps.com/>; The BioValley: <http://www.biovalley.com/public/index.html>; the Biopole (http://www.biopole.ch/english/index_en.html); the ProteomeValley: <http://www.proteomevalley.com/info/who.html>

II. Strengths of Switzerland and Canada in Genomics

This section compares Canadian and Swiss scientific output and the level of protection of their intellectual property. The analysis uses data from the Science Citation Index (SCI) and the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO). The aim is to identify fields where Canada and Switzerland can cooperate in a mutually beneficial manner.

Global Position in Genomic Science and Technology

The following table shows the ranks of leading countries in the production of scientific papers. As one can see, Canada publishes more papers than Switzerland (respectively ranking 6th and 11th), but Switzerland produces more papers *per capita*, ranking first worldwide. The Swiss scientific community is also highly specialized in genomic research – ranking 2nd, while the Canadian community occupies 9th place. The scientific impact of both countries' papers - measured with the impact factor – is about the same. Overall, Switzerland occupies a better position than Canada, ranking second globally, just below the U.S.A; Canada ranks 6th.

**Table 2 Rank of Leading Countries in Genomics
by Publication of Scientific Papers, 1990-1998**

Rank	Number of papers	Papers per inhabitant	Index of specialization	Relative impact factor	Global rank
1	USA	Switzerland	USA	USA	USA
2	Japan	Sweden	Switzerland	Switzerland	Switzerland
3	UK	Netherlands	France	Canada	UK
4	Germany	USA	Sweden	Netherlands	Netherlands
5	France	UK	Japan	UK	France
6	Canada	Canada	Netherlands	France	Canada
7	Italy	Australia	UK	Germany	Sweden
8	Netherlands	France	Australia	Sweden	Japan
9	Australia	Germany	Canada	Australia	Germany
10	Sweden	Japan	Germany	Spain	Australia
11	Switzerland	Italy	Italy	Italy	Italy
12	Spain	Spain	Spain	Japan	Spain
13	USSR/Russia	USSR/Russia	USSR/Russia	USSR/Russia	USSR/Russia

Source: Science Citation Index and United Nations Statistics Division

Table 3 shows how countries perform in terms of patenting activities in the U.S.A. Canada has the 5th rank in terms of absolute number of patents granted in the U.S. while Switzerland comes 9th. Nevertheless, similar to the pattern observed for papers, the Swiss exhibit greater output *per capita*, although Canada follows closely. The index of specialization shows that in contrast to what was

observed for publications Canada is considerably more specialized than Switzerland in patenting. However, the Swiss genomic community achieves the highest growth rate for patents, followed by Australia and Canada. The global rank is, however, favourable to Canada (2nd); Switzerland ranks 6th.

Table 3 Ranking of Leading Countries in Genomics by Patenting Activities in the USA, 1990-1999

Rank	Number of patents in USA	USA patents per inhabitant	Index of specialization	Growth	Global rank
1	USA	USA	Australia	Switzerland	USA
2	Japan	Netherlands	Netherlands	Australia	Canada
3	Germany	Switzerland	Canada	Canada	Australia
4	France	Canada	USA	France	Netherlands
5	Canada	Sweden	USSR/Russia	USA	France
6	Netherlands	Japan	UK	Germany	Switzerland
7	UK	Australia	Spain	Sweden	Germany
8	Australia	France	France	Netherlands	Sweden
9	Switzerland	Germany	Sweden	UK	Japan
10	Sweden	UK	Germany	Italy	UK
11	Italy	Italy	Switzerland	Japan	Spain
12	Spain	Spain	Italy	Spain	Italy
13	USSR/Russia	USSR/Russia	Japan	USSR/Russia	USSR/Russia

Source: United States Trademark and Patent Office and United Nations Statistics Division

Positioning Canada and Switzerland for Cooperation

The ranks of leading countries in scientific fields (Table 4) reveal the most promising field for mutually beneficial cooperation. Biomedical Research – the core field of genomics with 58% of the papers – is the most promising field for collaboration, with Switzerland ranking 3rd and Canada 5th. Clinical medicine is also of interest, with Switzerland coming in in the 5th place and Canada in 7th.

While Canada is very strong in Biology where it ranks 1st, this is where Switzerland's performance is poorest, ranking only 10th. These positions are nearly inverted in Chemistry, where Switzerland ranks 1st and Canada 7th. However, Biology and Chemistry cannot be considered as core fields in genomics since they account for only 8% of publications.

Rank	Biology	Biomedical Research	Chemistry	Clinical Medicine
1	Canada	USA	Switzerland	USA
2	Australia	UK	USA	UK
3	UK	Switzerland	Sweden	Netherlands
4	USA	France	Germany	Sweden
5	Japan	Canada	France	Switzerland
6	Netherlands	Germany	Japan	Japan
7	Germany	Netherlands	Canada	Canada
8	France	USSR/Russia	UK	Italy
9	Spain	Australia	USSR/Russia	France
10	Switzerland	Sweden	Spain	Australia
11	Sweden	Japan	Netherlands	Germany
12	Italy	Spain	Australia	Spain
13	USSR/Russia	Italy	Italy	USSR/Russia
Papers (%)	21,343 (6%)	205,864 (58%)	7,240 (2%)	117,948 (33%)

Source: Science Citation Index and United Nations Statistics Division

In order to determine more precisely how both countries stand to draw the greatest benefits from collaboration, it is useful to examine in which specialties both countries exercise leadership, that is, where both occupy at least the 7th rank. Table 5 shows that in the core field of genomics, Biomedical Research, collaboration could be prioritized in the following specialties: Biochemistry & Molecular Biology, Biomedical Engineering, Cell Biology, Cytology & Histology, Microbiology, and Physiology.

In Clinical Medicine, which is the second core field of genomics, a number of specialties could present potentially interesting collaboration projects. These are Anaesthesiology, Endocrinology, Nephrology, Neurology & Neurosurgery, Pharmacology, Respiratory System and Veterinary Medicine. Finally, two other specialties could be of interest, namely Optics and Behavioural Science & Complementary Psychology. In Biology, the General Zoology specialty could provide great opportunities.

**Table 5 Global Rank of Leading Countries in Genomics
by Field and Sub-Field, 1990-1998**

Field	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Biology							
Ecology	USA	Australia	UK	Canada	Sweden	Switzerland	Netherlands
General Biology	USA	Australia	Germany	Switzerland	Canada	UK	France
General Zoology	Canada	Australia	Japan	USA	Switzerland	Sweden	UK
Biomedical Research							
Biochemistry & Molecular Biol.	USA	Switzerland	Germany	France	Canada	UK	Japan
Biomedical Engineering	Switzerland	UK	Japan	Canada	Germany	USA	Sweden
Cell. Biol., Cyt. & Hist.	Switzerland	USA	France	Germany	Canada	Italy	Netherlands
Embryology	UK	Switzerland	USA	Germany	France	Canada	Spain
General Biomedical Research	USA	UK	Switzerland	France	Canada	Germany	Netherlands
Genetics & Heredity	UK	Netherlands	Canada	USA	Australia	Switzerland	France
Microbiology	Netherlands	USA	Switzerland	France	Canada	UK	Germany
Misc. Biomedical Research	UK	Switzerland	USA	Canada	Spain	Australia	Japan
Physiology	USA	Switzerland	UK	Germany	Canada	France	Sweden
Virology	USA	UK	Germany	Canada	Netherlands	Australia	Switzerland
Chemistry							
Analytical Chemistry	USA	Canada	Japan	Sweden	Germany	Switzerland	Spain
Physical Chemistry	Sweden	France	USA	Germany	UK	Canada	Switzerland
Clinical Medicine							
Allergy	Australia	Switzerland	UK	Netherlands	Japan	Canada	USA
Anesthesiology	USA	Germany	Canada	France	Switzerland	UK	Japan
Cardiovascular System	USA	Netherlands	Canada	Japan	Germany	Sweden	Switzerland
Endocrinology	USA	Canada	Sweden	France	Switzerland	Australia	UK
Fertility	USA	Canada	Netherlands	UK	Australia	Sweden	Switzerland
General & Internal Medicine	UK	USA	Sweden	Canada	Netherlands	Switzerland	France
Misc. Clinical Medicine	UK	France	USA	Japan	Switzerland	Netherlands	Canada
Nephrology	USA	Canada	Switzerland	Germany	Japan	UK	Netherlands
Neurology & Neurosurgery	USA	Switzerland	Canada	Sweden	UK	Germany	France
Orthopedics	USA	Sweden	Canada	Japan	UK	Switzerland	Australia
Pathology	Netherlands	UK	USA	Switzerland	Japan	Canada	Germany
Pharmacology	USA	UK	Switzerland	Sweden	Canada	Japan	France
Respiratory System	UK	Canada	Switzerland	Japan	France	USA	Italy
Surgery	USA	Sweden	Japan	UK	Switzerland	Canada	Germany
Veterinary Medicine	Australia	UK	Switzerland	Canada	USA	Japan	Netherlands
Mathematics							
Probability & Statistics	UK	USA	Australia	Canada	France	Spain	Switzerland
Physics							
Optics	USA	Germany	Switzerland	Sweden	Canada	France	Japan
Psychology							
Behavi. Sc. & Compl. Psy.	Canada	USA	Switzerland	UK	Germany	France	Netherlands

Source: Science Citation Index and United Nations Statistics Division

* * *

The analysis presented above is an aggregate evaluation of the Swiss and Canadian genomic communities' performance. The fact that the scientific fields listed present the greatest opportunities for *planned* collaborative research does not mean that mutually beneficial collaboration could not be performed at an individual level between leading researchers in other fields.

III. Leadership Structure of Switzerland in Genomics Research

This section examines the distribution of papers in genomics by sector, institution, city and researcher. The Medline database is used here, since more than 91% of papers in genomics are published in journals classified in the fields of Biomedical Research and Clinical Medicine. From 1990 to 2001, Switzerland published around 17,000 papers in genomics that were indexed by Medline (measured by first author of paper and Swiss affiliation).

Distribution of Papers in Genomic Science by Sector

In Switzerland, a little less than 58% of papers in genomics are authored by researchers affiliated with universities (Figure 2). The health sector also plays an important role in the development of research in genomics since nearly 25% of papers are authored by researchers affiliated with a health centre, a medical clinic or a hospital (including university hospitals). Governmental organizations authored a little more than 2% of papers, while private enterprises authored almost 14% of papers. Other institutions have authored less than 1% of papers and authors from unknown institutions, 2.5%. The output by private enterprises is exceptionally high and is similar to that of Denmark.

As Figure 3 clearly shows, the production of papers by universities is led by *Universität Zürich* and the ETHZ, with respectively 25% and 19% of the sector's output. The remainder of the leading institutions' production is distributed relatively evenly, *Universität Basel* accounting for 15%, University of Bern for 14%, University of Lausanne for 13% and University of Geneva for 12%. All these universities have published over a thousand papers during the 1990-2001 period.

Figure 4 lists the most active institutions in the health and hospital sector, the first three being university hospitals. The *Hôpitaux Universitaires de Genève* lead the sector, their 1,185 papers representing 25% of the sector’s output, while Zürich’s University Hospital ranks second with 20% and the *Centre hospitalier universitaire vaudois* in Lausanne ranks third with 15%. The following three institutions, the Basel Institute of Immunology (10%), the *Inselspital* located in Bern (9%) and the *Kantonsspital* located in Basel (8%) together account for close to 30% of this sector’s output while the Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research located in Lausanne (LICR) produced less than 5%.

As mentioned earlier, unlike in other countries, publications by private firms in Switzerland constitute a significant part (14%) of the papers published in the field of genomics. Table 6 shows that Novartis, which is Swiss-owned and located in Basel, is the principal contributor of this sector's performance with more than 1,500 papers representing nearly 60% of the sector's production. In Switzerland, this organization's output is surpassed only by the University of Zürich (2,325) and the ETH-Zürich (1,732). Other significant contributors are Hoffmann-La Roche (Basel, 566 papers, that is, a little less than 22% of the sector's output), Serono (Zug, 295 papers, or 11%) and the Nestlé Research Centre (Vevey, 130 papers, 5%). Together, these four firms represent more than 96% of the sector's total output. Importantly, Basel clearly stands out as the most important Swiss industrial hub in the field of genomics.

**Table 6 Ranking of Leading Enterprises in Genomics in Switzerland.
Number of Papers by City, 1990-2001**

Rank	Enterprise	Headquarters Location	Basel	Genève	Lausanne	Bern	Cham	Zürich	Visp	Bubendorf	Marly	Dubendorf	Others, unknown	total
1	Novartis	Switzerland (Basel)	1528											1528
2	F. Hoffmann-La Roche	Switzerland (Basel)	566											566
3	Serono	Switzerland (Zug)		295										295
4	Nestle Research center	Switzerland (Vevey)			130									130
5	Berna Biotech	Switzerland (Bern)				13								13
6	Jain PharmaBiotech	Switzerland (Basel)	13											13
7	Elchrom Scientific	Switzerland (Cham)					7							7
8	Lonza	Switzerland (Basel)	1						6					7
9	Pentapharm	Switzerland (Basel)	7											7
10	Bachem	Switzerland (Bubendorf)								5				5
11	Cosmital	Germany (Darmstadt)									5			5
12	Cytos Biotechnology	Switzerland (Zürich)						4						4
13	Givaudan	Switzerland (Genève)										4		4
	Others (n=17)		8			1		3					7	19
Total			2123	295	130	14	7	7	6	5	5	4	7	2603

Source: Science-Metrix (Medline)

Position of Swiss Cities in Genomic Science

Figure 5 shows that Zürich leads the country's output by city with a 30% share. The city hosts the first (University of Zürich) and second (ETH - Zürich) institutions in term of university level research and holds second rank in the health sector (*Universitätsspital*). Basel, with 26%, ranks second while Geneva is third (16%), Lausanne fourth (13%) and Bern fifth (11%). These six cities account for more than 95% of the Swiss scientific paper output.

Leading Swiss Researchers in Genomic Science

We have just seen that Zürich is the most active city in terms of research in genomics. In fact, 68% of the leading researchers are located in that city and 42% at the University of Zürich alone. This comes as no surprise since the city ranks first and second amongst universities and second in the health and hospital sector. Two Nobel laureates, Prof. Rolf Martin Zinkernagel of the Department of Pathology at University of Zürich and Prof. Kurt Wüthrich of the *Institut für Molekularbiologie und Biophysik* at ETHZ, respectively rank first and second as leading researchers. Zinkernagel is also listed in ISI's Highly Cited authors, together with Prof. Hans Hengartner (Institute of Neuropathology at the University Hospital of Zürich) and Prof. Hugh Robson Macdonald (Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research, Lausanne). Finally, it is worth mentioning that 32% of the leading researchers are active in immunology and 21% in biochemistry.

* * *

The distribution of research in genomics in Switzerland is concentrated in the cities of Zürich and Basel and, to a lesser extent, in Geneva, Lausanne and Bern. The University of Zürich has the largest output (2,325 papers), the ETHZ comes second (1,732 papers) and ranking third, reflecting the dynamism of the private sector, comes Novartis, a Basel based firm (1,528 papers). Although the cities of Zürich and Basel are in the lead in term of output by city, Part I has shown that organizations in Geneva and Lausanne, under the umbrella of the NCCR-Genetics, are aggressively promoting research in genomics and that these cities should not be overlooked.

Annex Ia - Swiss Universities Performing Research in Genomics

University	Department
Universität Zürich	Proteomics Centre (Veterinary Faculty) http://www.proteomicscenter.unizh.ch/
	Institute of Plant Biology http://www.unizh.ch/botinst/
	Institute of Zoology http://www.zool.unizh.ch/e/research/index.html
	Institute of Molecular Biology http://www.unizh.ch/imb/
	Institute of Biochemistry http://www.biochem.unizh.ch/research/gruetter/index.html - project10
Universität Zürich <i>and</i> ETHZ (The Swiss Federal Institute of Technology – Zürich)	Functional Genomics Center Zürich (FGCZ) http://www.fgcz.unizh.ch/
	Neuroscience Center Zürich http://www.neuroscience.unizh.ch/e/groups/hock00.htm
ETHZ (The Swiss Federal Institute of Technology – Zürich)	Institute of Animal Sciences (Department of Agriculture and Food Science) http://www.inw.agrl.ethz.ch/index_en.html
	Department of Biology http://www.rereth.ethz.ch/biol/biol.inst_overview.html
	Institute for Molecular Biology & Biophysics http://www.mol.biol.ethz.ch/
	Institute of Biotechnology http://www.rereth.ethz.ch/biol/biotechnologie/biotechnologie.prof_overview.html
	Institute of Cell Biology http://www.rereth.ethz.ch/biol/zellbiologie/zellbiologie.prof_overview.html
	Institute of Biochemistry http://www.rereth.ethz.ch/biol/biochemie/biochemie.prof_overview.html
	Institute of Microbiology http://www.rereth.ethz.ch/biol/mikrobiologie/mikrobiologie.prof_overview.html
	Institute of Toxicology http://www.rereth.ethz.ch/biol/toxikologie/toxikologie.prof_overview.html
Universität Basel	Department of Mathematics http://www.stat.math.ethz.ch/
	Institute of Zoology http://www.zoo.unibas.ch/index.html
	The Biozentrum http://www.biozentrum.unibas.ch/Research/research.html
	Botanical Institute (Plant Physiology section) http://www.unibas.ch/bothebel/molbio/molbio.htm

Universität Bern	Institute of Cell Biology http://www.izb.unibe.ch/
	Institute of Plant Sciences http://www.botany.unibe.ch/index.htm
	Department of Clinical Pharmacology http://www.ikp.unibe.ch/
Université de Lausanne	Institut de Biologie animale http://www.unil.ch/iba/en_index.htm
	Institute of Genetics and Microbial Biology http://www.unil.ch/igbm/english.html
	Comparative Genometrics http://www.unil.ch/comparativegenometrics/index.html
Université de Genève	University of Geneva's Transfer of Technology Office http://www.unige.ch/unitec/english/
	Département de zoologie et de biologie animal http://www.unige.ch/sciences/biologie/biani/
	Département de biologie moléculaire http://www.molbio.unige.ch/

Source: Science-Metrix (Internet)

Annex Ib - Swiss University Hospitals Performing Research in Genomics

Hospital	Department
Hopitaux Universitaires de Genève (HUGs)	Division de Génétique Médicale) http://medgen.unige.ch/
	Genomic Research Laboratory (Division of Infectious Diseases) http://infobi.hcuge.ch/QuickPlace/medinter/PageLibraryC1256B3D003E3678.nsf/h_Toc/cc76097a0192cb0bc1256b6b00407da5/?OpenDocument
	Département de Biochimie médicale http://www.expasy.org/BIOMED/
	Department of Genetics and Microbiology http://www.genmi.unige.ch/
Universitätsspital (Zürich)	Département de morphologie http://www.medecine.unige.ch/fm/morpho2.html
	Institute of Neuropathology http://www.unizh.ch/pathol/neuropathologie/index.html
	Institut für Medizinische Virologie http://www.research-projects.unizh.ch/med/unit41600/index.htm
	Ordinariat für Molekulare Psychiatrie (Psychiatrische Universitätsklinik) http://www.research-projects.unizh.ch/med/unit43500/index.htm - 43511
	Institute of Clinical Pathology http://www.research-projects.unizh.ch/med/unit43100/area108/index.htm
	Physiologisches Institut http://www.research-projects.unizh.ch/med/unit43400/index.htm
	Departement für Frauenheilkunde http://www.research-projects.unizh.ch/med/unit41300/index.htm
Centre hospitalier universitaire vaudois (CHUV)	Institute of Physiology http://www.unizh.ch/physiol/general/index.shtml
	Unité de Génétique Moléculaire http://www.hospvd.ch/public/chuv/genmol/home.htm
Pharmazentrum (Basel)	Institute of Biochemistry http://www.unil.ch/ib/iresearch.htm
	Basel Institute for Immunology http://www.pharmazentrum.unibas.ch/Kontakt/Immunologie/immunologie.html
Inselspital (Bern)	Human Molecular Genetics http://www.cx.unibe.ch/dkf2/Humangenet/MolHumE.htm

Source: Science-Metrix (Internet)

Annex II Companies Active in the Fields of Genomics, Proteomics and Bioinformatics in Switzerland

This annex comprises enterprises that were active in genomics between 1990 and 2002 or that acquired firms active in genomics during those years.

Apotech Corporation
Ch. des Croisettes 22
CH-1066 Epalinges
Switzerland
Tel: +41 21 654 7053
Fax: +41 21 654 7055
Email: info@apotech.com
Internet: <http://www.apotech.com/>

Apoxis SA
Biopôle
Chemin des Croisettes 22
CH-1066 Epalinges
Switzerland
Tel: +41 (21) 654 70 60
Fax: +41 (21) 654 70 65
Email: info@apoxis.com
Internet: <http://www.apoxis.com/>

Arpida
Dammstrass 36
4142 Münchenstein
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 417 9660
Fax: +41 61 417 9661
Email: contact@arpida.ch
Internet: www.arpida.ch/default.htm

Axovan Ltd.
Gewerbestrass 16
CH-4123 Allschwil
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 487 76 76
Fax: +41 61 487 76 00
Email: info@axovan.com
Internet: <http://www.axovan.com/index1.htm>

Bachem AG
Hauptstrasse 144
4416 Bubendorf
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 935 2323
Fax: +41 61 935 2325
Internet: <http://www.bachem.com/>

Berna Biotech AG
Rehhagstrasse 79
CH-3018 Bern
Switzerland
Tel: +41 31 980 61 11
Fax: +41 31 980 67 75
Email: info@bernabiotech.com
Internet: www.bernabiotech.com

Bioresco Ltd
Bundesstrasse 29
CH-4054 Basel
Switzerland
Tel: +41 (61) 273 77 00
Fax: +41 (61) 273 77 03
Email: contact@bioresco.ch
Internet: <http://www.bioresco.ch/>

Bioxal - Protein Expression Facility
BioPôle
Chemin des croisettes 22
CH-1066 Epalinges
Switzerland
Tel: (+41) 21 65 47 120
Fax: (+41) 21 65 47 125
Email: info@bioxtal.com
Internet: <http://www.bioxtal.com/>

Bruker Biospin AG
Industriestr. 26
8117 Fällanden
Switzerland
Tel: +41 1 825'91'11
Fax: +41 1 825'96'96
Email: sales@bruker-biospin.ch
Internet: <http://www.bruker.ch/index.html>

CSEM SA
Centre Suisse d'Electronique
et de Microtechnique
Rue Jaquet-Droz 1
P.O. Box CH-2007 Neuchâtel
Switzerland
Tel: +41 32 720 5111
Fax: +41 32 720 5700
Internet: www.csem.ch

Cilag AG
Hochstrasse 201
8205 Schaffhausen
Switzerland
Tel: +41 52 630 9111
Fax: +41 52 630 9444
Email: cilag@cilch.jnj.com
Internet: <http://www.cilag.ch/indexE.htm>

ClusterSolutions
Route de la Chocolatière 26
1026 Echandens
Switzerland
Internet: <http://www.clustersolutions.com/>

Cosmital SA
Bereich Toxikologie
Route de Chésalles 21
PLZ / Ort 1723 Marly 1
Switzerland
Tel: +41 26 435 25 55
Email: mbracher@cosmital.ch

Cytion SA
Bipôle
Chemin Des Croisettes 22
Épalinges
Switzerland
Tel: +41 21 654 70 30
Fax: +41 21 654 70 40
Email: info@cytion.com
Internet: <http://www.cytion.com/>

Cytos Biotechnology AG
Wagistrasse 25
Postfach CH-8952 Zurich-Schlieren
Switzerland
Tel.: +41 1 733 47 47
Fax: +41 1 733 47 40
Email: info@cytos.com
Internet: www.cytos.com/default.asp

DiagnoSwiss S.A.
Rte de l'Île-au-Bois 2
C/o Cimo S.A. - CP
CH - 1870 Monthey
Switzerland
Tel: +41 24 471 49 00
Fax: +41 24 471 49 01
Email: info@diagnoswiss.com
Internet: <http://www.diagnoswiss.com/>

Dictagene
4, chemin de la Vulliette
CH-1000 Lausanne 25
Switzerland
Tel: +41 21 785 60 60
Fax: +41 21 785 60 61
Email: contact@dictagene.ch
Internet: <http://www.dictagene.ch/>

Dionex (Switzerland) AG
Solothurnerstrasse 259
CH-4600 Olten
Switzerland
Tel: +41 62 205 99 66
Fax: +41 62 205 99 60
Internet: <http://www.dionex.com/>

Elchrom Scientific
Gewerbstrasse 8
CH-6330 Cham
Switzerland
Tel: +41 41 743 25 35
Fax: +41 41 743 25 36
Email: elchrom@access.ch
Internet: www.elchrom.com

Fluka Chemie GmbH
Industriestrasse 25
CH-9471 Buchs SG
Switzerland
Tel: +41 81 755 25 11
Fax: +41 81 755 28 15
Internet: <http://www.sigmaaldrich.com/>

GeneProt
2, rue du Pré-de-la-Fontaine
1217 Meyrin (Geneva)
Switzerland
Tel: + 41 22 719 39 00
Fax: + 41 22 719 39 99
Email: info@geneprot.com
Internet: <http://www.geneprot.com/>

Geneva Bioinformatics (GeneBio) S.A.
25 Avenue de Champel
CH- 1206 Geneva
Switzerland
Tel: +41 22 702 99 00
Fax: + 41 22 702 99 99
Email: info@genebio.com
Internet: <http://www.genebio.com/>

Givaudan SA
5, Chemin de la Parfumerie
1214 Vernier
Switzerland
Tel: +41 22 780 9111
Fax: +41 22 780 9150
Email: corp.communications@givaudan.com
Internet: <http://www.givaudan.com/>

GlaxoSmithKline S.A.
Talstrasse 3-5
CH-3053 Münchenbuchsee
Switzerland
Tel: +41 31 862 21 11
Fax: +41 31 862 22 02
Internet: <http://ch.gsk.com/>

Hoffmann-La Roche
Group Headquarters
Grenzacherstrasse 124
CH-4070 Basel
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 688 1111
Fax: +41 61 691 9391
Email: Corporate Webmaster
Internet: www.roche.com/home

Jain PharmaBiotech
Blaesiring 7
CH-4057 Basel
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 692 44 61
Fax: +41 61 692 44 61
Email: info@pharmabiotech.ch
Internet: <http://pharmabiotech.ch/>

Lonza Group Ltd
Muenchensteinerstrasse 38
CH-4002 Basel
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 316 81 11
Fax: +41 61 316 91 11
Email: info@lonzagroup.com
Internet: www.lonza.com/group/en.html

MCL Medizinische Laboratorien,
Chännelmattstrasse 9
CH-3186 Düringen
Switzerland
Tel: +41 26 492 72 72
Fax: +41 26 492 72 80
Email: info@mcl.ch
Internet: <http://www.mcl.ch/index2.htm>

Nestlé Suisse SA
C.P. 3521800 Vevey
Tel: +41 21 924 51 24
Fax: +41 21 924 54 38
Email: presse@ch.nestle.com
Internet: www.nestle.ch/fr/default.asp

Novartis Pharma Suisse SA
Südbahnhofstrasse 14d
CH-3001 Berne
Switzerland
Tel: +41 31 377 51 11
Fax: +41 31 377 52 11
Email: info.bern@pharma.novartis.com
Internet: www.novartis.ch/cgi/fr/index.asp

PENTAPHARM LTD
Engelgasse 109
CH-4002 Basel
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 7064848
Fax: +41 61 3199619
Email: sales-pharma@pentapharm.com
Internet: <http://www.pentapharm.ch/>

Robapharm AG
Gewerbstrasse 18
CH-4123 Allschwil
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 487 88 88
Fax: +41 61 487 88 99
Email: info@robapharm.ch

Serono Pharmaceutical Research Institute
14, Chemin des Aulx
1228 Plan-les-Ouates, Geneva
Switzerland
Tel: +41 22 706 9666
Email: georg.feger@serono.com
Internet: <http://www.spri.serono.com/>

Solvias AG
Klybeckstrasse 191
Postfach CH-4002 Basel
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 686 61 61
Fax: +41 61 686 65 65
Email: info@solvias.com
Internet: <http://www.solvias.ch/E/main.html>

Syngenta International AG
Postfach CH-4002 Basel
Switzerland
Tel: +41 61 323 23 23
Internet: www.syngenta.com/

Valibio sa
Chemin des Croisettes 22
Épalinges
Switzerland
Tel: +41 21 654 71 70
Fax: + 41 21 654 71 89
Email: info@valibio.ch
Internet: <http://www.valibio.ch/>

Veterinaria AG
Postfach CH-8045 Zürich
Switzerland
Tel: +41 1 455 31 11
Fax: +41 1 455 31 40
Email: info@veterinaria.ch
Internet: www.veterinaria.ch/

ZLB Bioplasma AG
Wankdorfstrasse 10
CH-3000 Bern 22
Switzerland
Tel +41 31 344 4444
Fax: +41 31 344 5555
Email: info@zlb.com
Internet: www.zlb.com